

Interaction of iron Schiff base complex with orthoamino phenol in aqueous surfactant micelles – an electrochemical and spectroscopic analysis

Pradyut Sarma^{*a}, Prabin Kumar Boruah^b and Okhil Kumar Medhi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Arya Vidyapeeth College, Guwahati-781 016, Assam, India

E-mail : gu_123456@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Gauhati University, Guwahati-781 014, Assam, India

Manuscript received online 30 November 2012, revised 30 January 2013, accepted 15 April 2014

Abstract : Iron(III) complex of Schiff base ligand ($[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^{+}$) interacting with *o*-aminophenol in aqueous surfactant micelles is studied as functional model of dioxygenase enzyme. Aqueous surfactant micelles have provided the biomimetic environment for the study. The pK_a of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{+}$ is 7.7 ± 0.2 in CTAB, 7.4 ± 0.2 in SDS and 7.6 ± 0.2 in Triton X-100 micelles. At low pH (when $\text{pH} < \text{pK}_a$) the aqua cationic species $[\text{LFe}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{+}$ is the major species, whereas at the high pH ($\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$) hydroxo species $[\text{LFe}^{\text{III}}(\text{OH})]$ is predominant in micellar solutions. Reacting *o*-aminophenol to $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{salen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{+}$ in aqueous SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 micelles, at pH 10.5, a new CT band in the range 420–440 nm has developed indicating the monodentate binding mode of the phenolate substrate. $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(o\text{-aminophenol})]$ exhibits an anodic shift of potential with respect to that of parent complex. The reaction kinetics of the oxygenation reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(o\text{-aminophenol})]$ in different micellar medium are studied.

Keywords : Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), sodiumdodecylsulphate (SDS), Triton X-100, isosbestic point, diffusion coefficient, cyclic voltammerty.

Introduction

The oxygenase enzymes catalyze reactions of dioxygen with organic substrate in which oxygen atoms from dioxygen are incorporated into the final oxidized product. These enzymes can be divided into dioxygenase, which direct both atoms of oxygen into the final product and mono-oxygenase, where one atom of oxygen from dioxygen is found in the product and the other has been reduced to water¹⁻³.

Dioxygenase enzymes are known to contain heme iron, non-heme iron, copper or manganese. Que (Jr.)^{1,2}, Funabiki³ and their coworker had proposed that the substrates whose oxygenations are catalyzed by these enzymes are very diverse, as are the metal binding sites; so different mechanisms operates in these different systems. Intradiol and extradiol dioxygenase are two main subclasses of this dioxygenase mechanism. Intradiol catechol dioxygenase utilizes Fe^{3+} or Mn^{2+} (sometimes) whereas, Fe^{2+} ion is utilized by extradiol catechol dioxygenase. Catechol-1,2-dioxygenase (CTD) and protococatechuate-3,4-

dioxygenase (PCD) are two important bacterial non-heme iron enzymes. The active site geometry of protococatechuate-3,4-dioxygenase has confirmed the coordination of the two tyrosine and two histidine residues and water (OH^{-}) in a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry¹⁻⁷ as depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Metal co-ordination sites of the crystallographically characterized mononuclear non-heme iron enzyme.

Catechol dioxygenase serves as a part of nature's strategy for degrading catechol and poly catechols in the environment. They are mainly found in solid bacteria and

act in the last step of transforming aromatic precursors into aliphatic products.

This work is shaped to study the kinetics of the interaction of iron-Schiff base complex with phenolate substrate, like ortho-aminophenol, with the help of spectroscopic and electrochemical techniques. The afford is directed toward investigating the phenolate-to-Fe^{III} charge transfer spectra and redox behaviour of the complex as well as their reactivity towards the phenolate substrate (i.e. *o*-aminophenol). The salen ligand provides the right coordination geometry of the synthetic models for the active sites of the non-heme iron enzymes. The phenolate moieties of the Schiff base can mimic the two tyrosine (Tyr) coordination, while the imine functionalities and co-ordinated imidazoles enzyme provide some correspondence to the histidine (His) coordination in a non-heme iron enzyme. The interaction of phenolic substrate like ortho-aminophenol with Fe(salen) complex can provide a better understanding of oxidative cleavage mechanism for the phenolate substrate. Phenolic waste products from paper industries and oil refineries cause a major threat to surrounding areas. A afford to work out a path for the conversion of toxic phenolic products into less toxic aliphatic byproducts would be of great significance⁸⁻¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Calculation of CMC values :

Depending on the nature of the surfactants medium the electronic spectrum of [Fe(salen)]⁺ complex has exhibited one band in the region 324 nm to 330 nm at pH below pK_a and another in the region 379 nm to 390 nm at pH above pK_a (Table 1).

The ferric complex shows an identical change in absorbance with increasing concentration of all the three

Table 1. Electronic spectral data of [Fe(salen)]⁺ complex in aqueous surfactant at various pH (Temperature 298 K)

Complex	λ_{\max}	pH	λ_{\max}	pH	λ_{\max}	pH
	(SDS)		(CTAB)		(Triton X-100)	
[Fe(salen)] ⁺	324, 480	6.5	327	6.5	330, 470	6.5
	390		386		379	

surfactants. The variations of the absorbance for the iron(III) complex are examined against a particular wavelength. For example, absorbance of the complex [Fe(salen)]⁺ is changed with the gradual increase in concentration of surfactant and this variation is monitored at a particular wavelength λ_{\max} 386 nm¹¹ (Table 1).

The critical micellar concentration (cmc) of CTAB, SDS and Triton X-100 for [Fe(salen)]⁺ are measured as follows. To obtained cmc spectrophotometrically, stock solution of the ferric complex of 5.0×10^{-5} M is prepared. Solutions of the surfactants are then prepared using the ferric complex solution as solvent. Using the method of Corrin and Harkins¹¹ the stock ferric complex solution is then titrated into 25 mL of the surfactant ferric complex solution and the absorbance measured at 386 nm at various dilutions of the surfactants. This allowed the determination of the absorbance of a constant concentration of ferric complex solution as a function of the surfactant concentration (Fig. 2). Below the cmc, the ferric complex sparingly dissolves in the aqueous surfactant solution and the absorbance of the solution remains low. At the cmc, a sudden rise in the solutions absorbance is observed, as the complex is encapsulated in micelles and

Fig. 2. Change in absorbance of [Fe(salen)]⁺ with the increase in surfactant concentration. ([Fe(salen)]⁺ = 3×10^{-3} M, pH = 6.5, Temperature 298 K).

dissolves in solution. Above the cmc, the absorbance of the solution increases linearly with increasing concentrations. This is an indication of micellization of the complex under investigation. The critical micellar concentration (cmc) calculated from Fig. 2 and the values are $3.3\text{--}7.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1.3\text{--}4.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $6\text{--}6.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ for SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 respectively¹¹. However it is important to note that the exact value of cmc depends on various factors, such as ionic strength, temperature and the nature of the solute. The experiment is performed in a N_2 atmosphere to minimize CO_2 absorbance with changes the pH and therefore the absorbance¹¹.

Redox potential values are also concentration of solution dependent and it might be helpful for indication of encapsulation of complexes in concern solution. The $E_{1/2}$ of the Fe^{3+}/Fe^{2+} redox couples of the $Fe(\text{salen})$ complex in water at 298 K (pH \approx 6, using acetate buffer) is $-0.321 V$. Gradual addition of surfactants to the aqueous solution of $[Fe(\text{salen})]^+$ induces a positive shift and it continues to increase until a maximum concentration level has reached (i.e. cmc level). This trend account for the considerable stabilization of the redox centre provided by the increasing concentration of the surfactant solutions, towards oxidation. This implies that the complex has acquired some sort of stabilization with respect to oxidation because of this micellization. The increase in potential values also reflects the stability of the Lewis acidity of the iron center with approach to the cmc level¹².

Electrochemistry is a useful technique for determination of critical micellar concentration of (cmc) surfactants. In this measurement, the solutions are deoxygenated by bubbling N_2 gas for at least 5 to 10 min. A continuous flow of N_2 is also arranged over the solution throughout the experiment so as to prevent O_2 redissolving in the solution. In the electrochemical measurements the potential sweep rate is 100 mV/s. A $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ $[Fe(\text{salen})]Cl$ solution (fixed) and a $NaNO_3$ (fixed) with varying concentration of surfactants are used. The cleaned electrode is mounted in the cell, and an oxidation-reduction cycle (ORC) is applied to the working electrode with potential scan $-1.0 V$ to $+1.0 V$. For the determination of the cmc of surfactants by cyclic voltammetry, a series

of solutions are prepared at a definite concentration of the redox active material ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) and the supporting electrolyte ($0.3 M$); the concentrations of the surfactants are varied. The half wave potential, $E_{1/2}$, of each solution are measured and plotted against the concentration of surfactant. The abrupt changes in the values of the initial slopes are considered as the cmc points¹². Above this threshold level (cmc level) the $E_{1/2}$ values never undergoes abrupt change and almost assume constant value. Such dependence of the mid point potential of complex on the concentration of a surfactant indicates encapsulation of the complex in surfactant^{11,12}. The calculated values of cmc are $3.3\text{--}4.9 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1.9\text{--}3.1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $5.6\text{--}6.3 \times 10^{-4} M$ in SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 respectively (Fig. 3). These values are in close agreement with the cmc values obtained by spectroscopic data.

Fig. 3. Change of $E_{1/2}$ of $[Fe(\text{salen})]^+$ complex with CTAB concentration.

Electrochemical results of $[Fe(\text{salen})]^+$ in water ethanol solution :

The cyclic voltammogram of $[Fe(\text{salen})]^+$ complex (pH 4.5) (acetate buffer) in ethanolic solution (1 : 1 v/v) is the quasi-reversible system. The peak separation ΔE_p is nearly constant for scan rate up to $0.05 V s^{-1}$ and then increases with higher scan rate, the current function i_{pc} / \sqrt{v} increases with scan rate. In addition to that, the ratio of cathodic to anodic peak current (i_{pc}/i_{pa}) is close to unity with increasing scan rate. The mid point redox po-

Table 2. The $E_{1/2}$ value for the $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ couple in $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ in different surfactants

Complex	Solvent	$E_{1/2}$ (V)		E_{pc} (V)	E_{pa} (V)	ΔE_p (V)	Scan rate (V s^{-1})
		CV	OSWV				
$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$	$\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{EtOH}$	-0.292	-0.293	-0.234	-0.350	0.116	0.1

tential $E_{1/2}$ is found to be -0.292 ± 0.002 V (Ag-AgCl electrode) at scan rate 0.1 V s^{-1} (Table 2). It is important to note that during recorded these voltammograms the solvent are deoxygenated by purging with N_2 gas.

Electrochemical results of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ in aqueous surfactant :

The cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$, encapsulated in aqueous surfactant micelles (SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100), at $\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$ (≈ 8.5) produces only the forward peak (i.e. cathodic peak). The potential values of the $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ couple of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex ion in the micelles are found to be -0.380 V (in SDS), -0.325 V (in CTAB) and -0.456 V (Triton X-100) respectively (Table 3).

The comparative study of $E_{1/2}$ values for the $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ couple of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex ion in aqueous medium and in surfactant medium, made it clear that micellization of the complex can cause positive shift of $E_{1/2}$ values. This implies that the complex has acquired some sort of stabilization with respect to oxidation because of this micellization. This may be due to encapsulation of the complex in micelles where the hydrophobic and the electrostatic interaction play an important role^{4,12}. It is seen that $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex encapsulated in CTAB undergoes more positive shift from the redox potential value of the complex in aqueous solution. This shift is

Table 3. Electrochemical results for $[\text{FeL}]^+$ complex in different surfactants

(L = salen)				
Complex	Solvent	pH	$E_{1/2}$ (V) OSWV ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$)	D_0
$[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{salen})]^+$	Water-EtOH (1 : 1 v/v)	6.0	-0.292	3.12
	SDS	6.0	-0.298	1.1
	CTAB	6.0	-0.204	1.4
	Triton X-100	6.0	-0.260	
$[\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{salen})]$	SDS	8.5	-0.380	0.51
	CTAB	8.5	-0.325	0.67
	Triton X-100	8.5	-0.456	

slightly lower in SDS and in Triton X-100 micelles.

CTAB is a cationic surfactant with positive trimethylammonium hydrophilic head group and hexadecyl hydrophobic tail group with Br^- as the counter ion. In cationic surfactant, positively charged complex part (i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$) undergo slight repulsive interaction which may also influence the Lewis acidity of the metal center. More positive shift of $E_{1/2}$ values of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ in CTAB micelles is a manifestation of this interaction and it implies that the complex has acquired some sort of stabilization with respect to oxidation because of this micellization¹².

Diffusion coefficient of $[\text{FeL}]\text{Cl}$:

The value of diffusion coefficient (D_0) are calculated by substituting the slope obtained from the linear i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ ($v < 0.05 \text{ V s}^{-1}$) plot in the Randles-Sevcik equation. The values of current function ($D_0 = 0.5\text{--}3.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) for the ferric complex in different micellar medium are of the same order as those observed for other iron(III) complexes undergoing a one electron reduction process. The i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ plot is linear, but the values of peak current ratio i_{pa}/i_{pc} (1.0–0.6) and the peak potential separation ΔE_p (69–140 mV) suggests fairly reversible to irreversible redox processes (Table 3)^{4,8,9,12}.

Measurements of pK_a values :

$[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]\text{X}$ (X may be Cl or ClO_3) complex is partially soluble in water. The X^- ion is present as counter ion in the complex and it can be detected by adding AgNO_3 solution to the aqueous complex solution. The Cl^- or ClO_3^- ions are quantitatively removed as the white precipitate of AgCl or AgClO_3 . In aqueous solution, Cl^- or ClO_3^- ions are replaced by water molecules $[\text{LFe}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Z}]^+$ ($Z = 1, 2$). However, increase in pH value of the solution may cause deprotonation of one axial aqua ligand giving rise to $[\text{LFe}^{\text{III}}\text{OH}]^+$ ^{11,13} as shown in the eq. (1) i.e.

The electronic spectrum for the proton exchange process

of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex in aqueous surfactant micelles are examined.

Eq. (1) clearly indicates the existence of two species (i.e. aqua species and hydroxo species) for the same $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]^+$ complex depending upon the pH range of the solution. At low pH (if $\text{pH} < \text{pK}_a$) the aqua cationic species $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ is the major component, on the other hand at high pH (if $\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$) deprotonation takes place and hydroxo species $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{LOH}]$ is predominant. These two different functioning are evident from the pH dependent spectral variation of ferric complexes in surfactant solution as exhibited in Fig. 4. This spectral representation has shown the growth of isosbestic point with the change in pH value. We have recorded the spectral change with pH value ranging from 3.5 to 10. At low pH ($\text{pH} < \text{pK}_a$) the band at 324–330 nm corresponds to aqua species of the complex ion $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{salen})]^+$. As pH value grows up, the band positioned at 380–390 nm range, slowly developed and at pH ranges above pK_a (high pH

Fig. 4. Electronic spectral variations of $3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex in aqueous CTAB as a function of measured pH range; spectra 1 ($\text{pH} = 3.5$) to spectra 12 ($\text{pH} = 10$).

$\sim 9-10$) the peak become predominant. It creates a nice isosbestic point at 348 nm, 291 nm and 270 nm. The existence of the isosbestic points suggests the formation of the following equilibrium.

Following similar line of reasoning, electronic spectrum of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{salen})]$ shows isosbestic points in the all three different surfactant mediums at the following wavelength positions, clearly indicating the presence of the two absorbing species.

Wavelength	Surfactant medium
300 nm 344 nm	SDS
270 nm 291 nm 348 nm	CTAB (Fig. 4)
350 nm 450 nm	Triton X-100

The pK_a values of the equilibrium (eq. (2)) in SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 micelles are analyzed, by a weighted non linear square fit, from the plot of absorbance as a function of pH using the Henderson-Hasselbalch equation¹³ (Fig. 5).

$$\text{pK}_a = m \cdot \text{pH} - \log \frac{[\text{A}^{m-}]}{[\text{AH}_m]} \quad (3)$$

where, AH_m and A^{m-} are the acid and conjugated base

Fig. 5. Change in absorbance of $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]^+$ complex in aqueous CTAB micelle as a function of pH at 390 nm. $\text{pK}_a = 7.67 \pm 0.01$, Temperature 298 K.

Table 6. Electrochemical results of [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] adduct in different surfactants

Complex	Solvent	$E_{1/2}$ (Volt)		ΔE_p (V)	i_{pc}/i_{pa} (μA)
		CV	OSWV		
[Fe ^{III} L(<i>o</i> -amph)]	SDS	-0.3675	-0.367	0.050	$1.16 \times 10^{-5} / (-)9.31 \times 10^{-6}$
	CTAB	-0.348	-0.348	0.058	$1.49 \times 10^{-5} / (-)8.37 \times 10^{-6}$
	Triton X-100	-0.329	-0.328	0.058	$8.5 \times 10^{-6} / (-)3.58 \times 10^{-6}$

no anodic wave. In these cyclic voltammogram, the plots of i_{pc} versus $v^{1/2}$ ($v < 0.5 \text{ V s}^{-1}$) are linear, revealing a diffusion controlled redox process.

On coordinating with phenolate substrate (i.e. *o*-aminophenol) with metal centre, the Fe^{III} \rightarrow Fe^{II} reduction process is shifted to more negative potential and new anodic wave developed (Fig. 6)^{4,8,18}. The cathodic potentials of the [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] adduct in all surfactant micelles are shifted to more negative values than that of the parent complex. It reveals that phenolic substrate coordination stabilizes iron(III) centre. The anodic peak of the cyclic voltammetric response of [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] may be due to the oxidation of the bound phenolate substrate (Fig. 6). The redox potential of the [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] is less negative than that of free phenolate substrate (-0.589 V) suggesting the stabilization of the coordinated phenolate anion (Table 6).

The $E_{1/2}$ values of Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} redox potentials of the

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of (a) [Fe(salen)(OH)] and (b) [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] complex encapsulated in CTAB. (pH = 10.5, Tris buffer, temperature 298 K, scan rate = 0.1 V s^{-1})

[Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] complex in three different micellar medium are following the trend :

SDS (-0.367 V) > CTAB (-0.348 V) > Triton X-100 (-0.329 V)

This trend suggests the decrease in Lewis acidity of the iron(III) centre on coordinating with *o*-aminophenol. The slightly more negative shift of $E_{1/2}$ values of Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} couple of [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] complex in SDS micelles is observed. This may be attributed to the stabilization of the Fe^{III} centre by co-ordinated phenolate ligand; the surfactant environment may also contribute to this. The incorporation of coordinated phenolate depresses the $E_{1/2}$ of the Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} couple of the parent complex by 40–150 mV and this reflects the decrease in Lewis acidity of the iron center on substrate binding and supports the suggestions that the Fe^{III} centre in the dioxygenases not only participates in the activation of the substrate but also facilitates the latter stages of the reaction^{11,12,16}.

The scan rate dependent cyclic voltammogram for the phenolate adduct {i.e. [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)]} in the three different micellar medium are recorded in Figs. 7(a) and 7(b). For these voltammetric response, the peak current ratio i_{pc}/i_{pa} is slightly higher than unity, the current function i_{pc}/\sqrt{v} is linear and independent of scan rate. Again, the peak currents i_{pc} and i_{pa} are linearly proportional to the square root of scan rates. All these electrochemical results indicate that the Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} redox process of monodentate *o*-aminophenol complex [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] in surfactant micelles is a diffusion controlled quasi-reversible redox process¹⁹.

Reactivity and kinetics study of [Fe(salen)(o-aminophenol)] adduct :

The oxygenation reactions of [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] adduct prepared *in situ* (using base) are investigated in various solvents like CH₃CN and aqueous surfactant medium. The oxygenation reaction of [Fe^{III}(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] adduct is studied by monitoring the slow

Fig. 7(a). Scan rate dependent cyclic voltammogram of 3×10^{-3} mol/L $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(o\text{-aminophenol})]$ adduct encapsulated in aqueous CTAB (pH = 10.5, Tris buffer, Temperature 298 K).

Fig. 7(b). Plot of peak current (i_{pc} and i_{pa}) vs the square root of the scan rate of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(o\text{-aminophenol})]$ adduct encapsulated in aqueous CTAB at pH 10.5.

change of the absorbance of the phenolate(π) \rightarrow iron^{III}($d\pi^*$) LMCT band (λ_{max} 436 nm). Gradual decrease of absorbance, at band position 436 nm (λ_{max}), with time indicates the decomposition of the substrate. The reactivity of the oxygenation reaction in aqueous surfactant medium can be exemplified by comparing the change of absorbance (λ_{max} 436 nm) both in presence or absence of O_2 .

The oxygenation reaction is carried out in all the three surfactant mediums using the following procedure. 2×10^{-4} M of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{salen})]^+$ is encapsulated in aqueous cationic surfactant micelle (CTAB). The pH of the solution is increased to 10.5 and equivalent molar amount of substrate (i.e. *o*-aminophenol) is made to react with complex. The interaction of substrate with Fe^{III} complex is evident from the change of colour of solution to red. The solution of substrate- Fe^{III} complex adduct is exposed to O_2 (air) at room temperature. The oxygenation kinetics is measured by monitoring the slow disappearance of the lower energy charge transfer band at λ_{max} 436 nm as shown in the Fig. 8(a).

The process is considered as pseudo-first order kinetics due to an excess of dioxygen^{6,12}. The electronic spectrum of the reaction mixture after 48 h has shown the disappearance of the 436 nm bands and appearance of the band around 300 nm indicating the completion of the oxygenation reaction. The rate constant (k_{obs}) was calculated by fitting the decrease in intensity of the band into the following equation applicable for relatively slow reaction

$$A = A_{\alpha} + (A_0 - A_{\alpha}) \exp(-k_{\text{obs}} t) \quad (4)$$

where t is the time, A , A_0 and A_{α} are the absorbance at the time t , 0 and α respectively, and k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant [Fig. 8(b)]. The second order rate constant K_{O_2} is then calculated from the equation^{4,6,12,14}.

$$K_{\text{O}_2} = \frac{K_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{O}_2]} \quad (5)$$

The oxygenation reaction of *o*-aminophenol- $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]$ adduct is also studied in anionic (SDS) and neutral aqueous micellar solution (Triton X-100) (Table 7). The rate of the oxygenation reaction indicates that rate of the reaction depends on the nature of the surfactants and Lewis acidity of the ferric complex. For $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})(o\text{-aminophenol})]$ adduct rate of the oxygenation reaction in surfactant micelles decreases in the order : SDS > CTAB > Triton X-100.

Conclusion

Several investigations have demonstrated that the reactivity of the model system is influenced by the Lewis

Fig. 8(a). (i) Progress of the reaction of [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] (generated *in situ*) encapsulated in CTAB with air at 298 K monitored by UV-Visible spectroscopy. The spectra are shown only at 1 min intervals; (ii) Gradual decrease of phenolate to Fe^{III} charge transfer band (inset).

Fig. 8(b). Plot of $\log(A - A_{\infty})$ vs time observed at 436 nm of [Fe(salen)(*o*-aminophenol)] (generated *in situ*) with O₂ at 298 K in CTAB.

acidity of the iron centre. A high Lewis acidity usually caused a high reactivity and that is one reason for the large number of model compounds containing pure nitro-

Table 7. Kinetic data for the oxidative cleavage of phenolate substrate (i.e. *o*-aminophenol) in different aqueous surfactants at 298 K temperature (analyzed after 24 h)

Complex	Solvent	K_{obs} (10^{-5} s^{-1})	K_{O_2} ($10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
[Fe(salen)(<i>o</i> -amph)]	CTAB	11.21 ± 0.21	9.58 ± 0.01
	SDS	19.3 ± 0.11	16.5 ± 0.11
	Triton X-100	7.31 ± 0.10	6.2 ± 0.01

gen donor ligands and the low number of complexes containing electron donating phenolate donors to mimic the tyrosine groups of the enzyme^{3,19}. The present coordinatively unsaturated iron(III) complex has bound to phenolate substrate with out replacing the already bound phenolate or any other of the primary ligands. On binding of the phenolate (*o*-aminophenol), two new phenolate \rightarrow Fe^{III} LMCT bands appear in the visible region, which is strikingly similar to that observed for the enzyme-substrate complexes in steady state conditions. So, the phenolate adducts containing only one bound donor are suggested as good synthetic model for an enzyme-substrate complex in which the equatorial but not the axial phenolate is bound to Fe^{III} 1-4,9,12,20,21.

We have characterized the experimental evidences to support the proposed ring cleavage of the ortho-amino phenol encapsulated in aqueous surfactant micelles above the critical micellar concentration. The natures of the surfactant micelle and ferric complexes have considerable influenced on the rate of the oxygenation reaction. The rates of dioxygenase of the complexes could be illustrated not on the basis of the Lewis acidity of the iron(III) centre alone but by assuming that the product release is the rate determining phase of the catalytic reaction, leading support to the electron-transfer mediated substrate activation mechanism by Que and co-worker^{1,2,21}. It is remarkable that the N-based complex confers as enhanced

reaction rate with efficient conversion of substrate to intradiol cleavage products.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligand, 1,2-bis(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)ethane or SalenH₂ :

The Schiff base ligand (salen) was synthesized according to the published procedures²⁰. Salicylaldehyde, ethylenediamine etc. were purchased from Merck chemicals. The synthetic procedure of the ferric Schiff base complex [Fe(salen)]Cl was previously reported²¹⁻²³. We used cationic micelle CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), anionic micelle SDS (sodium dodecylsulphate) and neutral micelles Triton X-100 in our experiments and all micelles were purchased from Sigma chemicals Co., USA and used without further purifications. Tris-buffers, tetramethylammonium bromide (TMAB) were obtained from Spectrochem. Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. The TMAB was used as counter ion in micelles. The supporting electrolyte NaNO₃ was obtained from BDH, UK. *o*-Aminophenol was obtained from Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. UV-Visible spectra were recorded in a Hitachi U-3210 model as well as in Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 UV/Vis spectrometer. The oxygenation kinetics experiments were performed in a 10 mm path length Thunberg quartz cuvette. pH dependent measurements were made by Adair Dupp. and Co. (India) model number DPH-77 pH meter. The pH electrode was SCE glass combined electrode which was standardized with known buffer solution. IR spectra was recorded a Perkin-Elmer RXIFT-IR spectrophotometer. Electrochemical experiments were performed on a BAS model 100A electrochemical analyzer. Bio Analytical system; USA. A three electrode cell assembly with nitrogen gas purging lines was used in combination with the analyzer. The working electrode is glassy carbon and the glassy carbon disc was polished by using 0.1 μm alumina and diamond slurry followed by sonication in an ultrasonicated bath. The reference electrode used was an Ag-AgCl (3 M NaCl, aqueous) electrode supplied by BAS. A platinum electrode was used as the auxiliary electrode. The supporting electrolyte was NaNO₃ and used about 100 times the concentration of the electro active species. The reference electrode potential was calibrated by measuring the $E_{1/2}$ of the ferrocene/ferrocinium couple in acetonitrile. Throughout the work 2%, 4% and 3% (w/v) solution of SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 are used. These

concentrations are adjusted above the level of critical micellar concentration (cmc). It favours the complete micellization of the complex²⁴ and also reduce the chance of any change in mid point redox potential value due to any minor fluctuation in the micelle concentration.

References

1. M. Costas, M. P. Mehn, M. P. Jensen and L. Que (Jr.), *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 939.
2. L. Que (Jr.) and M. Reynolds, *Met. Ions Biol. Syst.*, 2000, **37**, 505.
3. M. Higuchi, Y. Hitomi, H. Minami, T. Tanaka and T. Funabiki, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 8810.
4. R. Mayilmurugan, S. Eringathodi and P. Mallayan, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 6038.
5. M. Ferraroni, I. P. Solyanikova, M. P. Kolomytseva, A. Scozzafava, L. Golovleva and F. Briganti, *The J. Biolog. Chem.*, 2006, **279**, 27646.
6. M. Merkel, F. K. Merkel, M. Muller and B. Krebs, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **337**, 308.
7. A. Pui, I. Berdan, I. Morgenstern-Badarau, A. Gref and M. Perrée-Fauvet, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 2001, **320**, 1-2, 167.
8. D. K. Das, C. Bhattaray and O. K. Medhi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 4713.
9. T. Dhanalakshmi, M. Bhuvaneshwari and M. Palaniandavar, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2006, **100**, 1527.
10. T. Kurahashi, K. Oda, M. Sugimoto, T. Ogura and H. Fujii, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 7709.
11. (a) P. Sarma and O. K. Medhi, *J. Surface Sci. Technol.*, 2011, **27**, 1, 135; (b) M. L. Corrin and W. D. Harkins, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 676; (c) J. W. Ledbetter (Jr.) and J. R. Bowen, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 1345.
12. (a) J. H. Cameron and S. C. Turner, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, **23**, 3285; (b) A. B. Mandal, B. U. Nair and D. Ramaswamy, *Langmuir*, 1988, **4**, 736; (c) A. B. Mandal and B. U. Nair, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 9008.
13. D. A. Baldwin, H. M. Marques and J. M. Pratt, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1986, **27**, 245.
14. M. Velusamy and M. Palaniandavar, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 8283.
15. D. K. Das and O. K. Medhi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1998, 1693.
16. A. Qurari, M. Khelafi, D. Aggoun, G. Bouet and M. A. Khan, *Advance in Physical Chemistry*, 2011, **157484**, 11.
17. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
18. P. Sarma and O. K. Medhi, *Int. J. Chem. Res.*, 2011, **2**, 135.

Sarma *et al.* : Interaction of iron Schiff base complex with orthoamino phenol *etc.*

19. M. Pascaly, M. Duda, F. Schweppe, K. Zurlinden, F. K. Muller and B. Krebs, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 828.
20. M. M. Taqui Khan, N. H. Khan, R. I. Kureshy, A. B. Boricha and Z. A. Shaikh, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 1990, **170**, 213.
21. L. Que (Jr.), C. K. Richard and S. W. Lloyd, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 5373.
22. J. C. Moutet and A. Ourari, *Electrochimica Acta*, 1997, **42**, 2525.
23. R. Viswanathan, M. Palaniandavar, T. Balasubramanian and T. P. Muthiah, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 2943.
24. M. Zamurovic, S. Christodoulou, A. Vazaios, E. Iatrou, M. Pitsikalis and N. Hadjichristidis, *Macromolecules*, 2007, **40**, 5835.

